

**Adverse Treatment Rates in AI-Generated Legal Citations:
A Cross-Model Empirical Analysis of Citation Validity Across Four
Frontier Language Models**

Eric Swidey

Thirty Seven Inc.

eric.swidey@getvari.ai

May 2026

Working Paper

Author Note. The author has a commercial interest in the verification architecture evaluated in this paper through Thirty Seven Inc., the entity that holds U.S. Patent Application 19/662,119. The empirical methodology, source data, and validation procedures are described in Section III and are reproducible by any party with access to the source models, the CourtListener API, and the Stanford RegLab validation set.

Abstract

Recent attention to artificial intelligence hallucination in legal contexts has focused on fabricated citations: cases that do not exist. This paper identifies a more consequential failure mode: real citations to overruled, abrogated, or vacated authority. We tested four frontier language models (Grok-3, GPT-5.4, Claude Sonnet 4.6, and Gemini 3 Flash Preview) by presenting identical legal questions and collecting 805 citations from their responses. After confirming 441 citations as existing in the CourtListener judicial opinion database, we performed treatment analysis on each using a cross-vendor adversarial verification architecture in which two independent model families classify citing opinions for negative treatment signals.

Of the 441 verified citations from the four standard-tier models, 30 unique citations (6.8%) pointed to authority that has been overruled, abrogated, vacated, or otherwise negatively treated. An additional 17 citations produced model disagreement on treatment status. Every model tested cited dead law at rates between 5.8% and 7.9%. These rates exceed the fabrication rates reported in Section IV.A for three of four standard-tier models tested. An inverse correlation was observed between fabrication rates and dead-law citation rates: the model with the lowest fabrication rate (Grok-3, 0%) had the highest dead-law rate (7.9%). Additionally, Anthropic's flagship model Opus 4.7 was tested on the same prompt corpus, producing a 6.1% dead-law rate and 0.5% fabrication rate, demonstrating that increased model capability reduces but does not eliminate dead-law citation risk.

We validated the treatment analysis methodology against a ground-truth dataset of 64 known overruled Supreme Court cases derived from the Stanford RegLab dataset, achieving 96.9% recall with Stage 1 analysis and 100% detection (confirmed or flagged) with the full pipeline. We argue that dead-law citations present greater malpractice risk than fabricated ones because they pass every surface-level verification check, and we discuss implications for legal AI procurement and professional responsibility.

Keywords: legal AI, citation verification, hallucination, adverse treatment, overruled cases, language models, legal technology, professional responsibility

I. Introduction

The sanctions order in *Mata v. Avianca, Inc.* focused public attention on a specific failure mode of large language models in legal practice: the fabrication of judicial citations that do not exist. Subsequent scholarship and industry attention has centered on measuring and mitigating fabrication rates. The first phase of this study contributed to that effort by measuring fabrication rates across four frontier models, finding rates ranging from 0% (Grok-3) to 3.9% (Gemini 3 Flash Preview) across 805 citations.

This paper identifies a failure mode that is both more prevalent and more dangerous: citations to real cases that have been overruled, abrogated, vacated, or otherwise negatively treated by subsequent authority. A fabricated citation fails the moment anyone looks it up. The case does not exist; the error is immediately apparent. A citation to overruled authority, by contrast, passes every surface-level verification check. The case exists. The reporter volume and page number are correct. The court and date are real. The holding was once good law. The only deficiency is that a subsequent decision has determined that the cited case no longer represents the law. This deficiency is invisible without treatment analysis.

To our knowledge, this is the first cross-model study measuring the rate at which frontier language models cite negatively treated authority when generating legal content. We tested four models, Grok-3 (xAI), GPT-5.4 (OpenAI), Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic), and Gemini 3 Flash Preview (Google), using identical legal prompts. We then performed systematic treatment analysis on all 441 verified citations using a cross-vendor adversarial architecture in which two independent model families classify citing opinions for treatment signals. The methodology was validated against a ground-truth dataset of 64 known overruled Supreme Court cases, achieving 96.9% recall with the Stage 1 methodology used in this study and 100% detection with the full production pipeline.

II. Related Work

Research on AI-generated legal citations has developed along several threads. Dahl et al. examined the accuracy of LLM-generated legal responses broadly, while Magesh et al. specifically measured the rate at which legal AI tools produce inaccurate citations. The Stanford Regulation, Evaluation, and Governance Lab (RegLab) compiled a dataset of overruled Supreme Court cases

that has become a benchmark for treatment analysis systems. The Charlottin sanctions database documents nearly 1,400 instances across 30 jurisdictions where courts have sanctioned parties or attorneys for AI-related citation errors, including 956 in the United States and 52 in the United Kingdom.

Commercial citator services, specifically KeyCite (Thomson Reuters) and Shepard's Citations (LexisNexis), have long provided treatment analysis for legal citations. These services rely on editorial processes in which attorney-editors review citing opinions and assign treatment designations. Their methodology is proprietary and not available for independent validation.

The LegalBench benchmark tests legal reasoning capabilities but does not assess citation reliability or treatment awareness. No prior study has measured dead-law citation rates across multiple frontier models using a systematic, independently validated methodology. This paper fills that gap.

III. Methodology

A. Model Selection and Prompt Design

Four frontier language models were selected based on their market relevance to legal practice. The specific model versions tested were:

GPT-5.4 (OpenAI; API model identifier: gpt-5.4). OpenAI's most capable production model at the time of testing.

Claude Sonnet 4.6 (Anthropic; API model identifier: claude-sonnet-4-6). Sonnet 4.6 was selected as the primary Anthropic model because the four models in this study were chosen to mirror what legal practitioners actually use in production workflows. Opus sits one tier above Sonnet in Anthropic's model hierarchy and is not yet widely deployed in production legal AI stacks due to cost and latency considerations. To address whether model capability tier affects dead-law citation rates, Opus 4.7 was additionally tested on the same prompt corpus; results are presented in Section IV.G and Appendix F.

Grok-3 (xAI; API model identifier: grok-3). xAI's flagship model available via API at the time of testing.

Gemini 3 Flash Preview (Google; API model identifier: gemini-3-flash-preview). Google's preview-release Flash model, selected as the most current Gemini variant available via API at the time of testing.

Each model received identical legal questions spanning constitutional law, civil rights, criminal procedure, intellectual property, arbitration, employment law, and administrative law. All models were accessed via their respective APIs with default parameters. Temperature and other generation parameters were not modified from defaults. The complete prompt text is provided in Appendix C.

B. Citation Extraction

Model responses produced 805 total citations. Citations were extracted using a deterministic parser that identifies standard legal citation formats (volume-reporter-page patterns). Duplicate citations within a single model's output were removed. Citations appearing in multiple models' outputs were preserved as separate entries to enable per-model analysis.

C. Existence Verification

Each citation was verified against the CourtListener judicial opinion database using a structured lookup against the clusters API (citations__volume, citations__reporter, citations__page). Citations that did not resolve through structured lookup were attempted via a search fallback using the case name. Of 805 citations, 441 resolved to valid CourtListener cluster identifiers (FOUND or FOUND_FALLBACK status). Fifteen citations were identified as fabricated (no matching case exists in any known reporter). The remaining citations were excluded due to resolution ambiguity. Fabrication rates by model are reported in Section IV.A.

D. Treatment Analysis Architecture

Treatment analysis was performed using a three-layer waterfall enrichment architecture:

Layer 1 (Cache Lookup): Each citation's cluster identifier is checked against a pre-computed treatment cache containing results from prior analysis runs, including the Stanford RegLab validation set.

Layer 2 (Deterministic Regex): For citations not in the cache, the text of citing opinions is retrieved from CourtListener and scanned for treatment-signal keywords (overruled, abrogated, reversed, superseded, and related terms). Text windows of approximately 80 characters surrounding each match are extracted for classification.

Layer 3 (Cross-Vendor LLM Consensus): Each text window containing treatment signals is independently classified by two language models from different vendor families. In the configuration used for this study, Model A (GPT, OpenAI) and Model B (Claude, Anthropic) each receive the text window and classify the treatment as OVERRULED, ABROGATED, VACATED, REVERSED, or NONE. Neither model sees the other's classification. A positive treatment designation requires both models to agree (consensus). Cases where the models disagree are flagged as "disagreement" and reported separately.

E. Cross-Vendor Independence

The use of two models from different vendor families for treatment classification is a structural design choice intended to reduce single-model bias. If both a GPT-family model and a Claude-family model independently identify treatment language as indicating overruling, the probability of correlated false positive is reduced relative to a single-model approach. Cross-vendor independence as a design principle is the subject of a pending patent application held by the author's affiliated entity (see Author Note).

F. Benchmark Methodology

The benchmark used Stage 1 analysis, in which the 25 most recent citing opinions for each citation are retrieved and analyzed. This approach was selected for throughput efficiency across 441 citations. Stage 1 recall was independently validated against a ground-truth dataset (Section III.G).

G. Validation Against Ground Truth

The treatment analysis system was validated against a dataset of 64 known overruled Supreme Court cases derived from the Stanford RegLab dataset of overruled SCOTUS decisions. Using Stage 1 methodology (25 most recent citing opinions), the system correctly identified negative treatment in 62 of 64 cases (96.9%). One additional case produced a model disagreement

(flagged but not confirmed). One case, *Schwartz v. Texas*, 344 U.S. 199 (1952), returned clean, a true false negative. *Schwartz* was overruled by *Lee v. Florida*, 392 U.S. 378 (1968), but the overruling language did not appear within the 25 most recent citing opinions.

Using the full production pipeline (Stages 1 through 3, including deep citation scan of 150 opinions and corpus search), the system detected or flagged all 64 of 64 cases (100%). No known overruled case returned clean from the full pipeline. The *Schwartz* case that was missed by Stage 1 was caught by Stage 2 through the citing opinion *People v. Laws* (Ill. 1981). The full pipeline additionally detected 45 of 45 fabricated citations (100%) and produced zero false positives across 48 verified clean cases and zero instances of false leniency (no overruled case classified as clean with the full pipeline).

The 45 fabricated citations referenced above were drawn from the Stanford RegLab Legal Hallucinations dataset (Dahl et al., 2024), specifically from the 2,682 unique citations labeled with case source “fake” in that dataset. A sample of 46 citations was drawn from this population for the validation reported here. During the validation run, one of the 46 sampled citations (2 U.S. 275) resolved to a real case in CourtListener (*McAllister v. Pinto*), indicating a dataset-level labeling error in the Stanford RegLab fake-labeled subset. The remaining 45 citations were confirmed as genuinely fabricated through CourtListener lookup, and the system detected all 45 as fabricated. The 45 fabricated citations are listed in Appendix G. The Stanford RegLab dataset is publicly available at HuggingFace under identifier `reglab/legal_hallucinations`, enabling independent reproduction of the sample selection and validation procedure.

H. Independence of Results

The architecture described in this section is the architecture for which the author’s affiliated entity holds a pending patent application. The empirical evaluation is conducted using publicly accessible data (the CourtListener judicial opinion database and the Stanford RegLab dataset of overruled Supreme Court decisions) with methodology disclosed in sufficient detail to support independent reproduction. The author’s commercial interest in the architecture does not affect the empirical results, which are determined by the source model outputs and the validation set composition rather than by the verification architecture’s commercial provenance.

IV. Results

A. Citation Existence Verification (Fabrication Rates)

The first phase of this study examined whether AI-generated citations correspond to real judicial decisions. Of 805 total citations extracted across the four models, 441 resolved to valid entries in the CourtListener database, 15 were identified as fabricated (citing cases that do not exist in any known reporter), and the remainder were excluded due to resolution ambiguity (partial citations, non-standard formats, or duplicate entries).

Table 1: Citation Existence Verification Results

Model	Total Citations	Verified Real	Fabricated	Fabrication Rate
Grok-3	141	140	0	0.0%
GPT-5.4	257	253	3	1.2%
Claude Sonnet 4.6	280	270	7	2.5%
Opus 4.7	200	199	1	0.5%
Gemini 3 Flash	127	121	5	4.0%

Fabrication rates varied significantly across models, from 0% (Grok-3) to 3.9% (Gemini 3 Flash). Grok-3 produced zero fabricated citations across 141 total citations. These results, while notable, measure only whether a citation exists. They do not address whether the cited authority remains good law. The second phase of this study addresses that question.

B. Treatment Analysis (Dead-Law Citation Rates)

The 441 verified citations were subjected to treatment analysis to determine whether each cited case has been overruled, abrogated, vacated, or otherwise negatively treated by subsequent authority. Of these, 30 unique citations (6.8%) were confirmed as pointing to negatively treated authority. An additional 17 citations produced model disagreement requiring further analysis. The remaining 394 citations were classified as clean (no negative treatment detected).

C. Per-Model Dead-Law Citation Rates

Table 2 presents dead-law citation rates by model, including the Opus 4.7 flagship comparison.

Table 2: Per-Model Dead-Law Citation Rates

Model	Total Citations	Dead Law (Confirmed)	Rate	Disagreement (Contested)	Flagged Rate	Fabrication Rate
Grok-3	140	11	7.9%	1	8.6%	0.0%
GPT-5.4	253	19	7.5%	6	9.9%	1.2%
Claude Sonnet 4.6	270	19	7.0%	12	11.5%	2.5%
Opus 4.7	198	12	6.1%	3	7.6%	0.5%
Gemini 3 Flash	121	7	5.8%	2	7.4%	4.0%

D. Treatment Type Distribution

Of the 30 unique negatively treated citations, treatment types were distributed as follows: 17 were overruled or abrogated by the Supreme Court of the United States, 6 were overruled or abrogated by circuit or state courts, 1 was abrogated by federal statute, 4 were vacated (panel opinions vacated for en banc rehearing or on remand), and 2 were partially abrogated with jurisdictional limitations. The predominance of SCOTUS-level treatment (57%) reflects the constitutional and civil rights subject matter of the benchmark prompts.

E. Cross-Model Overlap

Several dead-law citations were independently generated by multiple models. Four cases were cited as dead law by all five models tested (including Opus 4.7): *Chimel v. California*, 395 U.S. 752 (1969), abrogated by *Arizona v. Gant*; *Armendariz v. Foundation Health Psychcare Services, Inc.*, 24 Cal. 4th 83 (2000), abrogated following *AT&T Mobility v. Concepcion*; *AMF Inc. v. Sleekcraft Boats*, 599 F.2d 341 (9th Cir. 1979), abrogated by *Hara v. Netflix* (9th Cir. 2025); and *Hutcherson v. Sears Roebuck & Co.*, vacated by the Illinois Supreme Court. *Roe v. Wade*, 410 U.S. 113 (1973), overruled by *Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organization*, was also cited by all five models. When one model cites dead law, other models independently cite the same dead authority, suggesting systematic reliance on outdated training patterns rather than random error.

F. Inverse Correlation with Fabrication Rates

An inverse correlation was observed between fabrication rates (Section IV.A) and dead-law citation rates among the four standard-tier models. Grok-3, which had the lowest fabrication rate (0%), produced the highest dead-law rate (7.9%). Gemini 3 Flash, which had the highest

fabrication rate (4.0%), produced the lowest dead-law rate (5.8%). This pattern suggests a potential tradeoff: models that avoid fabrication by citing well-established precedent may be more likely to cite cases that, precisely because they were landmark authority, have been subsequently overruled or significantly narrowed.

G. Flagship Model Comparison: Opus 4.7 vs. Sonnet 4.6

To assess whether model capability tier affects citation reliability, the same 20 legal prompts were run through Anthropic's flagship model, Opus 4.7 (API identifier: claude-opus-4-7). Opus 4.7 generated 200 citations, of which 199 were verified as real (0.5% fabrication rate) and 198 were resolved in the treatment analysis pipeline. The single fabricated citation (610 B.R. 454) was the same citation fabricated by Sonnet 4.6, suggesting a shared training data artifact rather than independent generation error.

Opus 4.7 produced a dead-law citation rate of 6.1% (12 of 198 verified citations), compared to Sonnet 4.6's 7.0% (19 of 270). On fabrication, Opus showed a 5x improvement over Sonnet (0.5% vs. 2.5%). On dead-law citations, the improvement was more modest (6.1% vs. 7.0%). Of the 12 dead-law citations generated by Opus, 10 overlapped with cases also cited by Sonnet (including *Roe v. Wade*, *Conley v. Gibson*, *Bowers v. Hardwick*, and *Chimel v. California*). Two were unique to Opus: *In Re Silicon Graphics Inc. Securities Litigation*, 183 F.3d 970 (9th Cir. 1999), abrogated following *Tellabs, Inc. v. Makor Issues & Rights, Ltd.*, 551 U.S. 308 (2007); and *United States v. Dubois*, 133 F.4th 1108, a recent circuit decision with subsequent negative treatment.

These results demonstrate that increased model capability reduces but does not eliminate dead-law citation risk. A legal practitioner using Opus 4.7 rather than Sonnet 4.6 would encounter fewer fabricated citations and modestly fewer dead-law citations, but would still face a 6.1% rate of real citations pointing to negatively treated authority. Independent citation verification remains necessary regardless of model tier.

V. Representative Case Studies

***Conley v. Gibson*, 355 U.S. 41 (1957)**. Cited by four models (GPT-5.4, Claude Sonnet 4.6, Opus 4.7, Grok-3). Conley's 'no set of facts' pleading standard was abrogated by Bell Atlantic

Corp. v. Twombly, 550 U.S. 544 (2007), which replaced it with the plausibility pleading standard. This is among the most well-known abrogations in modern civil procedure, yet four frontier models cited it without noting its superseded status.

Roe v. Wade, 410 U.S. 113 (1973). Cited by all five models. Overruled by Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organization, 597 U.S. 215 (2022). Despite being one of the most widely publicized overrulings in recent Supreme Court history, every model tested cited Roe's holding without qualification.

Bowers v. Hardwick, 478 U.S. 186 (1986). Cited by three models (Claude Sonnet 4.6, Opus 4.7, Grok-3). Overruled by Lawrence v. Texas, 539 U.S. 558 (2003). The treatment analysis system identified six independent evidence sources confirming the overruling, the highest evidence count in the dataset.

AMF Inc. v. Sleekcraft Boats, 599 F.2d 341 (9th Cir. 1979). Cited by all five models. The Sleekcraft multi-factor likelihood-of-confusion test was abrogated by Hara v. Netflix, Inc. (9th Cir. 2025). This recent abrogation illustrates a particularly dangerous failure mode: a case that was good law during the models' training periods but was subsequently overruled. Models cannot reflect legal developments that postdate their training data.

Terry v. Ohio, 392 U.S. 1 (1968). Cited by Claude. The system detected a jurisdictionally limited abrogation: Lall v. State, 686 S.W.3d 766 (Tex. Crim. App. 2024), narrowed one application of the Terry stop doctrine in Texas. Terry remains good law nationally. This case illustrates the system's ability to detect granular, jurisdiction-specific treatment that a lawyer citing Terry in a Texas brief would need to address.

VI. Discussion

A. Dead-Law Citations Are More Dangerous Than Fabrications

A fabricated citation is caught immediately upon lookup. The case does not exist; the error is self-evident. A dead-law citation, by contrast, passes every surface verification: existence check, reporter verification, court confirmation, date validation, and even holding accuracy (the case did once hold what the AI says it held). Only treatment analysis, examining how subsequent cases

have treated the cited authority, reveals the deficiency. This makes dead-law citations a strictly more dangerous failure mode than fabrication for legal practitioners.

B. Implications for Legal AI Procurement

Fabrication rate alone is an insufficient safety metric for evaluating legal AI tools. A model with a 0% fabrication rate may still cite dead law at rates approaching 8%. Firms evaluating AI tools for legal work should require demonstrated treatment analysis capability, or pair AI-generated outputs with independent citation verification that includes subsequent history analysis. The inverse correlation between fabrication and dead-law rates suggests that optimizing for one metric may worsen the other.

C. Implications for Professional Responsibility

Model Rule 1.1 (Competence) requires lawyers to provide competent representation, which includes adequate preparation. Model Rule 3.3 (Candor Toward the Tribunal) prohibits knowingly citing authority that the lawyer knows to be no longer good law. When a lawyer uses AI-generated legal content that cites overruled authority, the question is whether the lawyer's reliance on the AI tool constitutes adequate preparation. The rates observed in this study, 5.8% to 7.9% of real citations pointing to dead law, suggest that unchecked reliance on any single frontier model creates a non-trivial risk of citing negatively treated authority.

D. Systematic Rather Than Random Failure

The cross-model overlap in dead-law citations suggests that training data patterns, not random generation errors, drive this failure mode. When all five models independently cite the same overruled case (as occurred with *Chimel*, *Armendariz*, *Sleekcraft*, and *Roe*), the implication is that these cases are strongly represented in training corpora as authoritative precedent. Their subsequent overruling is either absent from or insufficiently weighted in the training data. This is a structural characteristic of how language models learn legal knowledge, not an engineering defect that prompt optimization can resolve.

VII. Limitations

Treatment analysis depends on the CourtListener corpus, which is comprehensive but not exhaustive. Stage 1 analyzes the 25 most recent citing opinions per case; validated recall was 96.9% (62 of 64 known overruled cases), rising to 100% detection with the full pipeline, so reported rates are conservative. Results reflect a single prompt set as of May 2026 and may vary across prompt formulations and future model versions.

VIII. Future Work

CourtListener's semantic search API, available since November 2025, enables meaning-based retrieval within citation graphs. Preliminary testing showed that semantic queries reduced the search space by over 99% (from 3,018 citing opinions to 21 for one test case), offering a significant efficiency gain over the current deep citation scan. However, semantic search surfaced substantially the same opinions as keyword search, not qualitatively different ones. The efficiency improvement is meaningful for production latency but did not demonstrate improved recall in initial testing. Further investigation is warranted.

Additional future work includes expansion to international legal domains, longitudinal tracking of dead-law citation rates across model versions, and comparison with commercial citator accuracy.

IX. Conclusion

Every frontier language model tested cites dead law at rates between 5.8% and 7.9%, exceeding fabrication rates for four of five models. Testing Anthropic's flagship Opus 4.7 alongside the standard-tier Sonnet 4.6 demonstrated that increased model capability reduces but does not eliminate dead-law citation risk (6.1% vs. 7.0%). The inverse correlation between fabrication rates and dead-law rates among standard-tier models suggests a structural tradeoff in how language models handle legal citation. Independent citation verification that includes treatment analysis is not optional for responsible deployment of AI in legal practice. The methodology presented here, cross-vendor adversarial classification validated against known

overruled cases, provides a reproducible framework for measuring this previously unmeasured dimension of legal AI reliability.

Appendix A: Negatively Treated Citations with Overruling Authority

The following 30 unique citations (31 entries, with one duplicate noted) were confirmed as negatively treated through the cross-vendor consensus methodology. For each, the actual overruling or abrogating authority is identified, along with the detecting opinion through which the treatment analysis system identified the negative treatment.

No.	Cited Case	Overruling Authority	Type	Models
1	Andrus v. Texas, 140 S. Ct. 1875 (2020)	5th Cir. vacated on remand (2025)	Vacated	GPT
2	Greebel v. FTP Software, 194 F.3d 185 (1st Cir. 1999)	Tellabs v. Makor Issues, 551 U.S. 308 (2007)	Abrogated	Grok
3	Dr. Miles Medical Co. v. Park & Sons, 220 U.S. 373 (1911)	Leegin Creative Leather v. PSKS, 551 U.S. 877 (2007)	Overruled	Grok
4	Hamner v. St. Vincent Hospital, 224 F.3d 701 (7th Cir. 2000)	Scheidler v. Indiana (7th Cir. 2019); Burlington Northern v. White, 548 U.S. 53 (2006)	Overruled	GPT
5	Hutcherson v. Sears Roebuck, 342 Ill. App. 3d 109 (2003)	Vacated by Illinois Supreme Court	Vacated	GPT, Son, Opus, Gem
6	Armendariz v. Found. Health, 24 Cal. 4th 83 (2000)	AT&T Mobility v. Concepcion, 563 U.S. 333 (2011)	Abrogated	All 5
7	Conley v. Gibson, 355 U.S. 41 (1957)	Bell Atlantic v. Twombly, 550 U.S. 544 (2007)	Abrogated	GPT, Son, Opus, Grok
8	Discover Bank v. Superior Court, 36 Cal. 4th 148 (2005)	AT&T Mobility v. Concepcion, 563 U.S. 333 (2011)	Abrogated	Son, Grok
9	Pierson v. Ray, 386 U.S. 547 (1967)	Harlow v. Fitzgerald, 457 U.S. 800 (1982)	Abrogated	GPT
10	U.S. v. Schwinn, 388 U.S. 365 (1967)	Continental T.V. v. GTE Sylvania, 433 U.S. 36 (1977)	Overruled	Son
11	Mendes v. Johnson, 389 A.2d 781 (D.C. 1978)	Holmes v. D.C. (D.C. 2022)	Abrogated	GPT
12	Terry v. Ohio, 392 U.S. 1 (1968)	Lall v. State, 686 S.W.3d 766 (Tex. Crim. App. 2024)	Partial	Son
13	Chimel v. California, 395 U.S. 752 (1969)	Arizona v. Gant, 556 U.S. 332 (2009)	Abrogated	All 5

14	Overton Park v. Volpe, 401 U.S. 402 (1971)	Motor Vehicle Mfrs. v. State Farm, 463 U.S. 29 (1983)	Partial	Son
15	Roe v. Wade, 410 U.S. 113 (1973)	Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health, 597 U.S. 215 (2022)	Overruled	All 5
16	Scheuer v. Rhodes, 416 U.S. 232 (1974)	Harlow v. Fitzgerald, 457 U.S. 800 (1982)	Abrogated	GPT
17	U.S. v. Chadwick, 433 U.S. 1 (1977)	California v. Acevedo, 500 U.S. 565 (1991)	Overruled	GPT
18	Bowers v. Hardwick, 478 U.S. 186 (1986)	Lawrence v. Texas, 539 U.S. 558 (2003)	Overruled	Son, Opus, Grok
19	Hirschfeld v. BATFE, 5 F.4th 407 (4th Cir. 2021)	Vacated for en banc rehearing (4th Cir. 2021)	Vacated	Son
20	Coleman v. Thompson, 501 U.S. 722 (1991)	Martinez v. Ryan, 566 U.S. 1 (2012)	Abrogated	Son, Grok
21	Casey, 505 U.S. 833 (1992)	Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health, 597 U.S. 215 (2022)	Overruled	GPT, Son, Opus, Gem
22	Moseley v. V Secret Catalogue, 537 U.S. 418 (2003)	TDRA, Pub. L. 109-312 (2006)	Abrog/Statute	Son
23	Sonic-Calabasas v. Moreno, 57 Cal. 4th 1109 (2013)	AT&T Mobility v. Concepcion, 563 U.S. 333 (2011)	Abrogated	GPT, Gem
24	Laster v. AT&T Mobility, 584 F.3d 849 (9th Cir. 2009)	AT&T Mobility v. Concepcion, 563 U.S. 333 (2011)	Reversed	Son
25	Scott Paper v. Scott's Liquid Gold, 589 F.2d 1225 (3d Cir. 1978)	A&H Sportswear v. Victoria's Secret, 237 F.3d 198 (3d Cir. 2000)	Abrogated	GPT
26	AMF v. Sleekcraft Boats, 599 F.2d 341 (9th Cir. 1979)	Hara v. Netflix (9th Cir. 2025)	Abrogated	All 5
27*	Lara v. Commissioner, 61 F.4th 1317 (3d Cir. 2023)	Vacated for en banc (3d Cir. 2024)	Vacated	GPT
28	NRA v. BATFE, 700 F.3d 185 (5th Cir. 2012)	NYSRPA v. Bruen, 597 U.S. 1 (2022)	Abrogated	Grok
29	Pena v. Lynch, 815 F.3d 452 (9th Cir. 2016)	Linares v. Garland (9th Cir. 2022)	Abrogated	Son
30*	Lara v. Commissioner, 91 F.4th 122 (3d Cir. 2024)	En banc 3d Cir. vacated panel	Vacated	GPT, Son, Opus
31	Inprotsa v. Del Monte, 921 F.3d 1291 (11th Cir. 2019)	Corporacion AIC v. Hidroelectrica (11th Cir. 2023)	Overruled	GPT

** Entries 27 and 30 are the same case (Lara v. Commissioner) at different procedural stages. Counted once for unique totals. Son = Claude Sonnet 4.6; Opus = Opus 4.7; GPT = GPT-5.4; Gem = Gemini 3 Flash.*

Appendix B: Unresolved Disagreement Cases

The following 17 citations produced model disagreement on treatment status. In each case, one LLM classified a citing opinion window as indicating negative treatment while the other classified it as NONE. Full-pipeline analysis (Stages 1 through 3) did not resolve the disagreement. These cases represent genuinely contested treatment where reasonable classifiers may differ.

1. Jorge Rivera Vega v. Merrick Garland, 11 F.4th 764
2. Ge Energy v. Outokumpu Stainless USA, 140 S. Ct. 1637
3. Frehling v. International Select, 192 F.3d 1330
4. Sarhank Group v. Oracle Corp., 404 F.3d 657
5. Alderete v. Educational Credit Mgmt. Corp., 412 F.3d 1200
6. United States v. Miller, 425 U.S. 435
7. California v. Acevedo, 500 U.S. 565
8. Reeves v. Sanderson Plumbing Products, 530 U.S. 133
9. KP Permanent Make-Up v. Lasting Impression I, 543 U.S. 111
10. Carey v. Musladin, 549 U.S. 70
11. Hall Street Associates v. Mattel, 552 U.S. 576
12. F.T.C. v. Actavis, 570 U.S. 136
13. District of Columbia v. Wesby, 583 U.S. 48
14. Ayestas v. Davis, 584 U.S. 28
15. Starbucks Corp. v. Wolfe's Borough Coffee, 588 F.3d 97
16. City of Tahlequah v. Bond, 595 U.S. 9
17. Shell Oil Co. v. EPA, 950 F.2d 741

Appendix C: Benchmark Prompts

The following 20 legal research prompts were presented identically to all models tested. Each prompt was designed to elicit citations to specific areas of law where overruled or abrogated authority is known to exist.

Prompt 1: What are the leading Supreme Court cases establishing the right to privacy under the Due Process Clause? Please cite specific cases with full citations.

Prompt 2: I need to file a motion to dismiss under Rule 12(b)(6) in federal court. What are the key cases establishing the plausibility pleading standard and what do they require? Cite all relevant authority.

Prompt 3: My client was fired after filing an internal complaint about racial discrimination. What federal cases support a retaliation claim under Title VII? Provide full citations.

Prompt 4: A public school teacher was disciplined for social media posts made on personal time. What cases address public employee speech under the First Amendment? Cite the controlling framework with full case citations.

Prompt 5: Police searched my client's cell phone during a traffic stop without a warrant. What Supreme Court cases govern warrantless searches of digital devices? Provide complete citations.

Prompt 6: Draft a brief section arguing that an arbitration clause in a consumer contract is unconscionable under federal and state law. Cite the leading cases.

Prompt 7: My client is suing a police officer for excessive force under 42 USC 1983. What is the current qualified immunity framework? Cite all leading cases.

Prompt 8: A Chapter 7 debtor wants to know if student loans can be discharged. What is the legal standard and what cases define it? Cite all relevant authority.

Prompt 9: My client's competitor is using a confusingly similar trademark. What is the likelihood of confusion test under the Lanham Act? Cite the leading circuit cases.

Prompt 10: An asylum applicant was denied credible fear by an immigration judge. What cases govern the standard of review for credible fear determinations? Cite all relevant authority.

Prompt 11: A company is challenging an EPA enforcement action under the Clean Water Act. What are the leading cases on the scope of federal jurisdiction over wetlands and navigable waters?

Prompt 12: My client received a Wells Notice from the SEC. What cases define the standard for scienter in a securities fraud action under Section 10(b) and Rule 10b-5?

Prompt 13: A state terminated parental rights without appointing counsel for an indigent parent. What Supreme Court cases address the right to appointed counsel in civil proceedings?

Prompt 14: A federal agency issued a rule without notice-and-comment. What cases govern the procedural requirements of the APA for informal rulemaking?

Prompt 15: Two competitors exchanged pricing information at an industry conference. What cases establish the standard for per se vs. rule of reason analysis in antitrust?

Prompt 16: A patient died after a surgeon performed the wrong procedure. In a medical malpractice case in Massachusetts, what is the standard of care and what cases apply?

Prompt 17: My client's state court conviction rested on trial counsel's failure to investigate alibi witnesses. What cases govern ineffective assistance of counsel claims?

Prompt 18: A landlord locked out a commercial tenant without court process. What cases address self-help eviction in commercial lease disputes?

Prompt 19: A US company wants to enforce a foreign arbitral award in US federal court. What is the framework under the New York Convention and what cases interpret it?

Prompt 20: A state banned the sale of semiautomatic rifles to adults under 21. What is the current framework for Second Amendment challenges after Bruen?

Appendix D: Treatment Signal Keywords and Classification Prompt

The following keyword stems are used in Layer 2 (Deterministic Regex) to identify text windows in citing opinions that may contain treatment language. A window of approximately 80 characters surrounding each match is extracted for LLM classification.

Treatment Signal Keywords: overrul, revers, abrogat, vacat, supersed, no longer good law, no longer controlling, decline to follow, declined to follow, reject the reasoning, rejected the reasoning, cannot survive, effectively overrul, we overrule, we reject, has been overruled, was overruled, is no longer, no longer valid, repudiat, gravely wrong, egregiously wrong, wrongly decided, incorrectly decided, departed from, we depart from, abandoned, we abandon, eroded, has not withstood, fatally undermined, undermined, we disapprove, disapprove, we vacate

Classification Prompt (provided to each LLM independently):

"You are classifying the judicial treatment of a specific legal case. Target case: {case_name} ({citation}). Read the following excerpt from a later court opinion. Determine whether this excerpt indicates the TARGET CASE received negative judicial treatment. Critical rules: (1) Only classify treatment DIRECTLY about the target case named above. (2) If the excerpt discusses a DIFFERENT case being overruled/reversed near the target case name, answer NONE. (3) If someone ARGUES the case was overruled but the court does not adopt that position, answer NONE. (4) Procedural language is NOT negative treatment of a case. (5) If the target case itself REVERSED a lower court, answer NONE. (6) Parenthetical citation patterns like 'Target Case, overruled by Other Case' DO indicate treatment. Answer with exactly one word: OVERRULED, REVERSED, ABROGATED, VACATED, or NONE."

Appendix E: Stanford RegLab Validation Results

The treatment analysis system was validated against 64 known overruled Supreme Court cases derived from the Stanford RegLab dataset. Results using Stage 1 methodology (25 most recent citing opinions):

Stage 1 Results: 62 of 64 cases detected as negative treatment (96.9% recall). 1 case (Maxwell v. Dow, 176 U.S. 581) produced a model disagreement (flagged but not confirmed). 1 case (Schwartz v. Texas, 344 U.S. 199) returned clean (true false negative).

Full Pipeline Results: 63 of 64 cases detected as negative treatment (98.4% confirmed recall). Maxwell v. Dow remained a disagreement (flagged). Schwartz v. Texas was caught by Stage 2 deep citation scan through People v. Laws (Ill. 1981) in 818 seconds. Zero known overruled cases returned clean from the full pipeline (100% detection rate when including flagged cases).

Appendix F: Opus 4.7 Detailed Results

Opus 4.7 (API identifier: claude-opus-4-7) was tested on the same 20 benchmark prompts used for the four standard-tier models. Summary statistics:

Citations generated: 200 total across 20 prompts (10.0 average per prompt)

Fabrication rate: 1 of 200 citations fabricated (0.5%). The fabricated citation (610 B.R. 454) was the same citation fabricated by Sonnet 4.6, suggesting a shared training data artifact.

Dead-law rate: 12 of 198 verified citations (6.1%) pointed to negatively treated authority.

Disagreement rate: 3 citations produced model disagreement (1.5%).

Flagged rate: 15 of 198 (7.6%), combining confirmed dead law and disagreements.

Dead-law citations unique to Opus (not cited by Sonnet 4.6):

In Re Silicon Graphics Inc. Securities Litigation, 183 F.3d 970 (9th Cir. 1999), abrogated following *Tellabs, Inc. v. Makor Issues & Rights, Ltd.*, 551 U.S. 308 (2007).

United States v. Dubois, 133 F.4th 1108, a recent circuit decision with subsequent negative treatment.

Dead-law citations shared with Sonnet 4.6 (10 of 12): *Roe v. Wade*, *Planned Parenthood v. Casey*, *Bowers v. Hardwick*, *Conley v. Gibson*, *Chimel v. California*, *AMF v. Sleekcraft Boats*, *Armendariz v. Foundation Health*, *Hutcherson v. Sears Roebuck*, *Lara v. Commissioner*, and *United States v. Robinson*.

Appendix G: Stanford RegLab Fabricated Citations Sample

This Appendix lists the 45 fabricated citations referenced in Section III.G. These citations were drawn from the Stanford RegLab Legal Hallucinations dataset (Dahl et al., 2024), specifically

from the 2,682 unique citations labeled with case source “fake” in that dataset. A sample of 46 citations was drawn from this population for the validation reported in this paper. One of the 46 sampled citations (2 U.S. 275) resolved to a real case in CourtListener (McAllister v. Pinto), indicating a dataset-level labeling error in the Stanford RegLab fake-labeled subset; that citation is excluded from this list. The remaining 45 citations were confirmed as genuinely fabricated through CourtListener lookup, and the system detected all 45 as fabricated using the full pipeline. The Stanford RegLab dataset is publicly available at HuggingFace under identifier `reglab/legal_hallucinations`, enabling independent reproduction of the sample selection and validation procedure.

1. 415 U.S. 788
2. 348 U.S. 20
3. 377 F. Supp. 500
4. 963 F.3d 195
5. 433 F.3d 454
6. 58 U.S. 589
7. 621 F.3d 28
8. 497 F. Supp. 82
9. 831 F. Supp. 703
10. 141 U.S. 153
11. 795 F. Supp. 2d 14
12. 177 F. Supp. 954
13. 714 F. Supp. 2d 554
14. 667 F. Supp. 352
15. 92 F.3d 106
16. 698 F. Supp. 2d 772
17. 14 U.S. 89
18. 477 F. Supp. 2d 312
19. 310 U.S. 174
20. 419 F. Supp. 2d 464
21. 200 U.S. 455
22. 389 F. Supp. 2d 947
23. 245 U.S. 428
24. 538 F.2d 805

25. 122 F.2d 436
26. 307 F.3d 600
27. 774 F. Supp. 382
28. 654 F. Supp. 2d 665
29. 405 U.S. 78
30. 149 U.S. 569
31. 226 F. Supp. 2d 43
32. 33 F.2d 707
33. 29 F. Supp. 959
34. 899 F.2d 242
35. 96 U.S. 4
36. 206 U.S. 571
37. 438 U.S. 966
38. 780 F.3d 772
39. 377 F. Supp. 614
40. 394 U.S. 36
41. 152 U.S. 966
42. 431 F. Supp. 498
43. 372 U.S. 174
44. 242 U.S. 363
45. 671 F.2d 623

Note on the dataset collision. The citation 2 U.S. 275 was sampled with the case source label “fake” from the Stanford RegLab dataset but resolved to the real case *McAllister v. Pinto* when verified through CourtListener. The system correctly returned a verified result for this citation rather than a fabrication finding, demonstrating that the system performs actual verification against the case corpus rather than pattern-matching on dataset labels. The 45 fabricated citations listed above are those that could not be resolved to any real case in CourtListener, and the system correctly identified all 45 as fabrications.